

Task analysis for toothbrushing

Scoring scale				
Not complete (with any form of prompting)	Physical prompting (continuous)	Physical prompting (Intermittent)	Verbal, Visual or gesture prompting	Complete independently
0	1	2	3	4

Session No. (.....).		Date:				
Phase:		Evaluator:				
Student name:		Total score:				
No.	Steps	Not complete	Physical prompting (continuous)	Physical prompting (Intermittent)	Verbal, Visual or gesture prompting	Complete independently
1	Pick up your toothpaste and teeth brush	0	1	2	3	4
2	Open toothpaste	0	1	2	3	4
3	Wet your toothbrush	0	1	2	3	4
4	Put toothpaste on the toothbrush	0	1	2	3	4
5	Close the toothpaste	0	1	2	3	4
6	Place the toothpaste in the place	0	1	2	3	4
7	Put the toothbrush in mouth	0	1	2	3	4
8	Brush the back of your top teeth	0	1	2	3	4
9	Brush the back of your bottom teeth	0	1	2	3	4
10	Brush the front of your top teeth	0	1	2	3	4
11	Brush the front of your bottom teeth	0	1	2	3	4
12	Rinse the toothbrush	0	1	2	3	4
13	Place toothbrush in the place	0	1	2	3	4
14	Spit the toothpaste into the sink	0	1	2	3	4
15	Rinse your mouth with water	0	1	2	3	4
16	Pick the towel	0	1	2	3	4
17	Dry your mouth and hands	0	1	2	3	4
Total score Percentage: Sum/68*100						